

“Women in Kerala” – Empowerment Achievements and Challenges

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Abstract

Women constitute 52 percent of the total population in Kerala compared with National average 48.18 % in 2017, but they are not enjoying their freedoms, equalities, privileges, on par with their male counterparts. Since the implementation of planning in Kerala, several policies and approaches were implemented to reduce inequalities between women and men. The status of women in Kerala is considering a serious matter. Aim of the paper is to investigate - whether the Women in Kerala are having the same status and rights as we are claiming regarding- equality in education, health, labour, employment and decision making. Women in Kerala are a valuable, healthy and educated resource and can contribute successfully in all aspects of the development of the state. An attitudinal change can be brought about by highlighting successful endeavours of women and by providing support systems for the multiple tasks they take up.

Keywords: Women empowerment, Kerala, Education and Literacy.

Introduction

In India, there exists an ample of gender inequality measured in terms of all the Gender Indices (GI) developed by UNDP. The Gender Development Index (GDI) value of India is 0.8411 with low equality in human development achievements between women and men (absolute deviation from gender parity of more than 15 percent). The GDI is used to measure the gender gaps in human development-achievement by three basic dimensions of human development-health, knowledge and living standards. In terms of Gender Inequality Index (GII) also, India ranks 127th with a GII value 0.524, while our neighbouring countries like China and Sri Lanka rank 36th (0.152), 80th (0.354) respectively. GII find out the gender inequalities, by using three major aspects of human development-a) “reproductive health”-measured by maternal mortality ratio and adolescent birth rate, b) “empowerment”- measured by proportion of parliamentary seats occupied by females and c) “economic status”- expressed as labour market participation measured by labour force participation rate of female and male population in the age of 15 years and older (Selvi and Pushpa, 2017).

Kerala State is recognized as a high gender development achievement in India. As per the Census 2011, the ratio of women in Kerala is 1,084, which is high compared to the national figure of 940.

Women constitute 52 percent of the total population in Kerala. Children aged 0-14 years represent 23.44 percent of the total population in Kerala; out of this, 48.91 percent are girls. It is surprise that 22 percent of the households in Kerala are female-headed compared to the national average of 11 percent. The State formulated a Policy on Women in 2009 and later a Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment (GEWE) Policy for 2014-2020. (Economic Review, 2017).

Literacy and Education

Kerala has the highest female literacy rate among the Indian States (92 percent) though a small gender gap exists. The basis of 'take-off' for the socio-cultural development and high female literacy rate is considered as achievement by Kerala women.

Enrolment is universal at the primary level. In the case of education, girl students constitute 49.01 percent of the total student enrolment in schools it could be found that there a gender gap between boys and girls. In terms of enrolment in higher secondary education, 51.84 percent Girl's outnumbered boy. Dropout rates are low for both boys and girls. At the tertiary level, the enrolment of girls is higher than boys. It could be evident that, girls constitute 68.49 percent of total enrolment for degree courses in various arts and science colleges in Kerala in 2017-18. At the level of post-graduation, the girls' position is highest at 67.01 percent. The situation is different, when the intake of girls in engineering colleges and polytechnics. Out of the total enrolled students, girls constitute only 38.24 percent in engineering colleges and 28.86 percent in polytechnics. Table 1 indicates the enthronement of girls and boys at different level.

Table 1 Enrolment of Girls and Boys at Different Levels 2017-18

	Boys	Girls	Total	% of Girls
School Education	1,888,462	1,815,356	3,703,818	49.01
Higher Secondary	183,979	198,072	382,051	51.84
Graduation	86,686	188,424	275,110	68.49
Post-Graduation	12,831	26,064	38,895	67.01
B Tech (Government, aided)	16,953	10,498	27,451	38.24
Polytechnic	7,646	3,103	10,749	28.86

Source: Directorate of Public Instruction; Directorate of Collegiate Education; Directorate of Technical Education, 2018.

Health Status of Women in Kerala

High social development is mostly reflected by the health status of women and men in Kerala, as well as to persons in other parts of the country. The majority of the health indicators are highly favourable to women in the State. Life Expectancy at the birth of women in Kerala at 76.9 years is the highest in India (all India average is 67.7 years). The demographic health indicators seem to be favourable to women of Kerala. Table 2 shows that Health status of women in Kerala.

Table 2 Health Status of women in India and Kerala

Sl. No.	Indicator		Kerala	India
1	Infant Mortality Rate		10	34
		Male	9	33
		Female	11	36
2	Mean age at marriage 2016	Female	23.1	22.2

3	Maternal Mortality Rate		46	130
4	The Expectancy of Life at Birth	Male	72.2	67.4
		Female	77.9	70.2

Source: Health management information system, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, GoI. SRS Bulletin, 2017.

Low maternal mortality rate and high female life expectancy in Kerala are highly attributed to the extensive public provisioning for maternal care in the State. The universal access to health care institutions helps to ensure maternal care as well as institutional delivery to all. The NFHS, 2015-16, as shown in Figure 6.2, indicates that the institutional delivery and antenatal care in Kerala are very high compared to all India average. Like-wise, adolescent pregnancy is very low in Kerala (Shown table 3). These achievements are the result of long decadal efforts of Kerala Government since its formation.

Table 3 India and Kerala - Maternal Care Indicators

	India			Kerala		
	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban	Rural	Total
Adolescent pregnancy	5	9.2	7.9	2.7	3.2	3
Mothers with Antenatal checkups	69.1	54.2	58.6	96.1	94.2	95.1
Institutional Births %	88.7	75.1	78.9	99.8	99.9	99.8

Source: NFHS, 2015-16

Participation in Economy

Women of Kerala perform better than their male counterparts in terms of many developmental indicators. But in terms of economic contribution, the outcome is not favourable to women. According to the 68th Round of NSSO (for the year 2011-12), a wide gap between male and female Labour Force Participation Rates (LFPRs) (principal and subsidiary status) is seen in the State. While that national average of female LFPR (per 100 persons) is 40.3 percent, but in Kerala is only 24.8 percent and that of the male are 57.8 percent. Himachal Pradesh has the highest female workforce participation rate of 49.8 percent. The North-eastern State like Nagaland, Sikkim, Manipur, Mizoram, Arunachal Pradesh and Meghalaya has higher FWPRs than Kerala.

Disaggregating by region, we find that the FLFPR in rural Kerala is lower than that of India. But in urban areas, the same is higher in Kerala than at all India level.

It is obviously seen that, the gender gap is widening over the period in levels of employment. The male WPRs show a mild upward trend or constancy, there is a declining trend in female WPRs. But Kerala women have a higher participation rate in urban areas vis-a-vis that at all India level. Table 4 reveals, that the WPR of men and women in Kerala.

Table 4 Work Participation Rate of Men and Women in Kerala

Year	Rural				Urban			
	India		Kerala		India		Kerala	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
1987-88	53.9	32.3	56.7	31.6	50.6	15.2	59.2	21.8
1993-94	55.3	32.8	53.7	23.8	52	15.4	56	20.3
1999-2000	53.1	29.9	55.3	23.8	51.8	13.9	55.8	20.3

2004-05	54.6	32.7	55.9	25.6	54.9	16.6	54.7	20
2009-10	54.7	26.1	56.4	21.8	54.3	13.8	54.7	19.4
2011-12	54.3	24.8	56.5	22.1	54.6	14.7	55.2	19.1

Source: Various Reports of NSSO.

Inequality in Wage Rates

In terms of wages and remuneration, there is a gender gap exists in the state as well as at the national level. The gender disparity in wage rate is prevalent not only in the informal or unorganised sector but also in regular or salaried employment. This is well explained in the below Chart. (Figure No 1).

Figure 1 Average Wage/Salary Received Per Day Employees of Age 15-59 Years, in Crore

Economic and social empowerments are complementary to each other. The economic empowerment of women is attained, when the women become an integral part of the labour force and be profitably employed without having to put up with the full burden of household responsibilities. It is necessary that, efforts are taken to reduce and redistribute unpaid household and care work and the state playing a central role in designing appropriate policies/schemes that support its reduction and redistribution.

Women’s Participation in Decision Making

Participation of women in decision making is an important indicator to measure the political empowerment. Women play a positive role in the decision making at home as well as in the policy decisions of the State. Their role at both levels is equally influential for the formation of an equitable and developed society. Women’s participation in decision making of the family is considered here in terms of three indicators as provided in NFHS, 2015-16. viz., the percentage of women who usually participate in the household decisions, the percentage of women having a bank/savings account operated by themselves and the percentage of women having a mobile phone that they use. As shown in Table 5, women in Kerala actively participate in the decision making the process more than their counterparts at all India level.

Table 5 Women's Participation in Decision Making

Indicators	India				Kerala			
	NFHS-4 (2015-16)			NFHS-3 (2005-06)	NFHS-4 (2015-16)	NFHS-3 (2005-06)		
	Urban	Rural	Total	Total	Urban	Rural	Total	Total
Currently, married women who usually participate in household decisions (%)	85.8	83	84	76.5	91.7	92.4	92.1	88
Women having a bank/savings account that they use (%)	61	48.5	53	15.1	70.3	70.8	70.6	27
Women having a mobile phone that they use (%)	61.8	36.9	45.9	NA	81.1	81.2	81.2	NA

Source: Women and men in India, 2017

The participation of women electors in the Lok Sabha elections has increased over the years from 46.63 percent in the third Lok Sabha election in 1962 to 66 percent in the election for 16th Lok Sabha (2014). The participation of women electors in Kerala is very high compared to all India average. But in terms of women's representation in Parliament, Kerala lags. In the 16th Lok Sabha, women constitute 12 percent of the total members of Parliament while one woman MP (5 percent) is from Kerala.

Crimes against Women

As per the crime statistics report of India in 2016, majority of cases were reported that under cruelty by husband or his relatives (32.6 percent) followed by assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty (25.0 percent) kidnapping & abduction of women (19.0 percent) and rape (11.5 percent). Uttar Pradesh reported 14.5 percent (46,972 out of 3, 29,067 cases) of total cases of crimes against women followed by West Bengal (9.6 percent) (33,052 cases) in 2016. Delhi UT reported the highest crime rate (59.9) compared to the national average rate of 53. In Kerala slightly above that is 53.4 percent.

Women Empowerment Programmes

Government of India implemented the number of programmes to empower women. Such as One Stop Centres, Anganwadi Karyakarti Bima Yojana, ICDS Training Programme, Ujjawala, Scheme of Widow Remarriage – Mangalya, Flagship Programme for Gender Awareness, Implementation of Dowry Prohibition Act, One-Day Homes to provide safe accommodation for women, Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana, Gender Park, NIRBHAYA, Construction of Nirbhaya Homes Sahayastham, Swadhar Greh, Working Women's Hostel and Mahila Shakthi Kendra are some of the major schemes under the department (Report on Women and Child Development Department, 2018).

Conclusion

It is recognised that, the inequality of gender roles in society results in women and men occupying different hierarchical social, economic and political positions within the household, workforce and community, which are prearranged in such a way as to leave women with little power economically, socially and politically. The flip side of this is men's socio-biological drive for mastery, manifested increasingly as violence against women who are also vulnerable in terms of their sex. Women are very often not able to make choices as individuals and what perhaps is in their best interest since they are positioned within relational and situational contexts which shape their actual choices,

rights and entitlements. The State and society have to work for demolishing these hierarchical impediments and expose the obscurantist ideas sought to be relied upon to subordinate women in the society. Kerala, which has a rich tradition of the renaissance movement of the 19th and 20th centuries, has taken up this dispute in right earnest with the State Government leading from the front.

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